

IMPLEMENTATION POLICY OF BPBD OF THE REGENT OF ACEH SINGKIL NUMBER 14 OF 2025 DUTIES AND FUNCTIONS IN DISASTER RISK REDUCTION IN ACEH SINGKIL REGENCY

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Abstract

This study aims to determine and describe the implementation policy of the Regional Disaster Management Agency (BPBD) of the Aceh Singkil Regent Number 14 of 2025 Duties and Functions in Disaster Risk Reduction in Aceh Singkil Regency. used. This study uses a descriptive qualitative method with data collection techniques namely interviews, documentation and non-participant observation. Through purposive sampling techniques obtained two key informants consisting of the Head of the BPBD Service then several community opinions. The results of field research show that the cause of frequent regional flooding in Aceh Singkil Regency is several technical problems that have not been resolved properly such as Technical and Infrastructure Problems, Spatial Planning Problems, Social and Compliance Problems, Government Coordination Problems and Funding and Political Limitations. So that these disasters are not resolved because several problems from the government itself have not been resolved by the Aceh Singkil Regent. If the problems from the government have been resolved properly, I as a researcher believe that the problem of flooding can be resolved effectively and efficiently.

Keywords: *Qanun Number 14 of 2025 Duties and Functions; Reduction; Natural Disasters.*

INTRODUCTION

Aceh Singkil Regency is a regency located at the southwestern tip of Aceh Province, Indonesia. Aceh Singkil is a division of South Aceh Regency and part of its territory is located in the Gunung Leuser National Park area. This regency consists of mainland and island areas. The islands that are part of this regency are the Banyak Islands. Singkil is the capital of this regency. As one of the regencies in Aceh that has the potential for disasters, Aceh Singkil has established an institution that focuses directly on disaster management, namely the Regional Disaster Management Agency (BPBD). The Aceh Singkil Regency BPBD is a regional apparatus formed to carry out the policy tasks and functions of disaster management in the region. The BPBD aims to ensure the implementation of disaster management in a planned, integrated, coordinated and comprehensive manner in order to provide protection to the community from the threats, risks and impacts of disasters. Previous Research: Rizal Wahyudha (2018) conducted a study on "Implementation of Flood Disaster Management by the DKI Jakarta Provincial BPBD." This study aimed to determine how flood disaster management is implemented in DKI Jakarta Province. This study used a qualitative descriptive approach.

The research results show that there are 3 points regarding the stages of flood disaster management that are carried out, namely (1) Pre-Disaster, (2) During the Disaster, and (3) Post-Disaster. The similarity between Rizal Wahyudha's research and this research is that both conducted a study on flood management conducted by the Regency BPBD, using qualitative descriptive research methods. The difference with that research is that this research is aimed at the provincial level, while the researcher's research was conducted at the district level. The implementation of disaster risk reduction can be effective if the government implements participatory disaster management by mobilizing various community structures and existing broadcasting institutions. Through this collaboration, government policies in disaster management will be effective by optimizing available local resources so that the community is not only seen as an object of disaster management but also as a subject responsible for community safety from various disasters.

DISCUSSION

1. First Discussion

In December 2016, Aceh Singkil was hit by a disaster, specifically in the Singkil and North Singkil Districts. This caused the community to have to set up a kitchen post because their houses were submerged in the disaster. Therefore, the Regional Disaster Management Agency (BPBD) supplied clean water for the needs of the residents' kitchen posts. In November 2017, Aceh Singkil was again hit by a disaster with a height of 50 cm to 70 cm, resulting in the connecting road between Aceh Singkil and the city of Subulussalam being cut off. In October 2018, several villages in Aceh Singkil District were again submerged by disasters and the worst was the disaster in Ujung Bawang Village, precisely in Singkil District, which required residents to build emergency bridges as a connection between the main road and their homes. The water level of the disaster was estimated to reach 80 cm to 1 meter.

Then in October 2019, Aceh Singkil was again hit by a disaster in Gunung Meriah District and North Singkil District, resulting in residents' houses being submerged, public facilities being submerged, rice fields and plantations being submerged, and residents' chicken livestock were also submerged, so that this greatly affected the residents' economy. There was also a disaster in 2020 caused by rainfall that occurred almost every day in September, resulting in the overflow of the Lae Cinendang River, causing disasters in several villages in Simpang Kanan District with a height reaching 1 meter. Then, in May 2021, Aceh Singkil was inundated by a disaster triggered by high-intensity rainfall, which inundated residents' homes. Several villages affected by the flooding disaster included Bulusemma Village in Suro District; Kampung Baru and Ketapang Indah Villages in North Singkil District; Lae Balno and Situban Makmur Villages in Danau Paris District; and several others. On January 31, 2023, another flood occurred in Aceh Singkil Regency, where heavy rainfall with high intensity caused the Sulampi River to overflow, resulting in flooding in Bulusema Village, Suro District, Aceh Singkil Regency.

2. Second Discussion

Public policy can be seen from the public administration dictionary of Chandler and Plano (1988:107), which states that public policy is the strategic use of existing resources to solve public or government problems. Chandler and Plano even believe that public policy is a form of continuous investment by the government for the benefit of the powerless in society so that they can live and participate in government. William N. Dunn (in Herabudin, 2016: 38), said that public policy is a series of interrelated choices made by government institutions or officials in areas related to government duties, such as security, defense, energy, health, education, public welfare, crime, urban areas and others. Factors hindering the implementation of the Regional Disaster Management Agency (BPBD)'s disaster risk reduction policy in Aceh Singkil Regency are circumstances, conditions, or events that hinder responsiveness. In general, these factors are divided into two categories: external and internal. Internal factors originate from within, while external factors originate from outside.

3. Internal Factors

Internal factors include the fact that the first obstacle is the still-unpredictable weather. The Aceh Singkil Regency Regional Disaster Management Agency (BPBD) predicts that there will be another rainy season in the near future. The next issue is the spatial planning of Singkil District, particularly regarding the arrangement of settlements around the river. The location of the settlements presents a significant challenge. The lack of adequate pumps is also a significant obstacle. Furthermore, there is the issue of poorly maintained infrastructure, such as embankment breaches in several locations. There is also wear and tear that sometimes goes beyond the planned scenario. BPBD infrastructure is still considered complete in terms of completeness, but the number of 16 is still insufficient to maximize BPBD performance. Therefore, BPBD efforts to address this include coordinating with the National Disaster Management Agency (BNPB) and the Aceh Provincial BPBD, through infrastructure grants and financial assistance. However, grants and financial assistance cannot be guaranteed every year. Therefore, to meet BPBD infrastructure needs through grant funds, maximized private and community funding.

4. External Factors

External factors that explain the differences in arguments. The next challenge is drainage and river silting. It can also be said that the Regional Disaster Management Agency (BPBD) still faces social issues. Community reluctance to evacuate is one of the main obstacles. The Regional Disaster Management Agency (BPBD) also faces other social issues, such as interceptions to divert people to other locations, or exploiting the situation to the detriment of the smooth flow of the disaster. Another challenge is the continued reluctance of many residents to leave their homes due to fear of losing their belongings. The Singkil BPBD recognizes these internal and external

obstacles and shortcomings. Therefore, the Aceh Singkil Regency Regional Disaster Management Agency (BPBD) in Singkil District has taken structured and measured action to address these obstacles.

Tables and graphs are numbered consecutively with the table title and number placed below the table. For example:

Table 1. Number of Sub-districts Affected by Floods

No	Year	Month	Subdistrict	Village
1	2016	December	North Singkil District	16
2	2017	November	Singkohor District	6
3	2018/2019	October	Singkil District/North Singkil District	27
4	2021/2023	May/January	Singkil District/Sub-district, Right Intersection	26

CLOSING

Based on Field Results That the implementation policy of BPBD Regent of Aceh Singkil Number 14 of 2025 Duties and Functions in the Disaster Risk Reduction policy in Aceh Singkil Regency has not been running optimally because there are still obstacles that have not been overcome such as the slow distribution of aid in terms of speed, distribution of aid to disaster victims is still slow due to limited facilities and infrastructure such as lack of rubber boats, no vehicles capable of reaching disaster locations that are difficult to access and also minimal human resources. In terms of accuracy, the aid distributed by the BPBD is sometimes not in accordance with the needs of the community due to the many requests from the community and limited sources of aid. In terms of accuracy, the service provided by the BPBD is still not satisfactory because the community still complains.

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